

(In-)Consistency Management in Modeling – Challenge 2026 – Construction of a Brake

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Abstract

The management of consistency, and in particular of inconsistency, plays a major role in the development of complex systems. This challenge aims to cover different aspects of this management, allowing solutions for (in-)consistency management in modeling to showcase their unique strategies on how to deal with aspects like inconsistency toleration, especially long-running potential inconsistency toleration. The community investigating the management of (in-)consistency, rooted in both academia and industry, is invited to respond to this challenge with submissions outlining how their specific approach, framework, or tool handles the inconsistency aspects described in this challenge. As many of the aspects described here still pose open research questions, submissions are not expected to implement all the mentioned aspects, but they should outline how the aspects could be handled. Thereby, the community can collect and discuss approaches and ideas, fostering collaboration and refining existing solutions as well as developing new ones. Therefore, we ask authors to emphasize the benefits but also explicitly the limitations of their respective approaches, and to also contribute their ideas.

Keywords

ICMM, inconsistency management, consistency management, model management, challenge, inconsistencies, consistency, management

1. Introduction

The engineering of safety-critical systems such as automotive brake systems relies on multiple overlapping models created by different disciplines and stakeholders [1]. These models describe shared aspects of the same system, such as physical structure, control logic, safety requirements, or calibration data, but do so with different purposes, assumptions, and levels of detail. As a consequence, inconsistencies between models are not exceptional situations but a normal and often unavoidable phenomenon during system development. Traditional consistency management approaches largely focus on the detection and immediate resolution of inconsistencies [2, 3], e.g., as a heuristic for eventual correctness [4]. However, industrial practice increasingly shows that this view is insufficient. In many situations, inconsistencies must be tolerated temporarily or even indefinitely: because information is incomplete, because responsibilities are distributed across teams, or because resolving an inconsistency too early would block progress. This challenge, therefore, adopts a perspective that treats inconsistencies as *managed entities* rather than errors that must always be eliminated immediately.

This challenge deliberately distinguishes between *detecting* inconsistencies and *managing* them. While inconsistency detection is a fundamental prerequisite and an active research topic in its own right,

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the primary focus of this challenge lies on what happens *after* an inconsistency has been identified, i.e., how it is represented, assessed, tolerated, monitored, and eventually resolved.

To avoid prescribing specific detection techniques or metamodels, the scenarios described in this challenge assume that at least some inconsistencies are known or suspected by stakeholders. This assumption does not imply that detection is trivial or solved, rather, it allows submissions to concentrate on long-running inconsistency management strategies beyond immediate error fixing. Approaches that explicitly address inconsistency detection as part of their solution are explicitly encouraged to discuss how detection integrates with subsequent management activities.

This challenge builds upon the spirit of the Model Management challenge [5], as well as the MULTI challenges, e.g., [6, 7, 8], but narrows the focus explicitly to (in-)consistency management. Instead of addressing heterogeneous modeling technologies or general model orchestration, the emphasis is on understanding, representing, explaining, tolerating, monitoring, and eventually resolving inconsistencies, especially those that persist over extended periods of time.

1.1. Introduction to (In-)consistency Management

Consistency management concerns the identification and handling of contradictions between overlapping descriptions of a system. Inconsistencies arise when two or more model elements that refer to the same concept or behavior cannot all be true at the same time under a given interpretation.

Inconsistency management goes beyond detection. It includes:

- the explicit representation of inconsistencies,
- reasoning about their causes and consequences,
- deciding whether an inconsistency is acceptable at a given point in time,
- monitoring how inconsistencies evolve,
- and supporting their eventual resolution.

A particularly challenging aspect is the handling of *long-running inconsistencies*, i.e., situations where contradictions are known and accepted for a significant duration of the development process. Such inconsistencies may be intentionally tolerated due to uncertainty, organizational constraints, or different levels of technological readiness.

1.2. Motivation for this Challenge

The goal of this challenge is to provide a concrete yet manageable case that allows approaches to inconsistency management to demonstrate how they support working *with* inconsistencies rather than only fixing them. The challenge is designed to foster discussion around questions such as:

- How can inconsistencies be represented and explained?
- How can the impact of inconsistencies be determined and quantified?
- How can they be tolerated safely over time?
- How does their criticality evolve?
- How do inconsistencies interact with system maturity and development progress?

Nature of Submissions. In contrast to implementation-oriented challenges, the goal of this challenge is not to require participants to realize the described scenarios in a concrete tool or modeling environment. Instead, submissions are expected to *conceptually discuss* how their approach, framework, or tool *would* handle the described inconsistency situations. Concrete implementations, example models, or tool demonstrations are welcome but not mandatory. The emphasis is on explicating assumptions, workflows, decision criteria, and limitations.

The challenge is not intended as a competition but as a forum for exchanging ideas, comparing strategies, and identifying open research questions.

2. Case Description – Brake System

The case study centers on an automotive brake system, chosen because it is safety-critical, multidisciplinary, and subject to continuous evolution throughout the product lifecycle [9].

2.1. Artifacts

The brake system is described using a small set of conceptual artifacts that are inspired by industrial RFLP-style engineering workflows (Requirements, Functional, Logical, Physical), as commonly used by OEMs and suppliers. Participants are free to realize these artifacts in any modeling notation or tool of their choice, as long as the described semantics and overlaps are preserved. The artifacts are intentionally defined at a conceptual level to remain agnostic of specific metamodels, tools, or standards.

- **Requirements Model:** Defines safety, performance, and regulatory requirements, including traceability to verification objectives and test descriptions.
- **Functional Model:** Captures the logical functions and behaviors of the brake system, independent of concrete hardware realization.
- **Structural Model:** Describes the physical and hardware decomposition of the brake system, including sensors, actuators, ECUs, and hydraulic components.
- **Control and Calibration Model:** Specifies control algorithms, parameters, thresholds, and calibration values used by the brake control software.
- **Verification and Test Results:** Document partial verification results, test outcomes, known deviations, and missing or planned test cases.

These artifacts overlap in their description of the same system aspects and therefore provide possibilities for the occurrence of inconsistencies.

2.2. Workflow Context

In industrial practice, the described artifacts typically evolve in a staged and partially overlapping workflow involving multiple roles and organizations. Requirements engineering, functional design, logical integration, and physical realization often proceed in successive phases, but with feedback loops and asynchronous updates. Downstream activities frequently start based on preliminary or outdated versions of upstream artifacts, which is a common and intentional practice to avoid blocking progress.

As a result, inconsistencies often arise not from modeling errors, but, e.g., from:

- version mismatches between evolving artifacts
- incomplete information in early phases
- organizational boundaries between teams or companies
- process constraints imposed by standards or release milestones

The inconsistency scenarios in this challenge should be understood as emerging naturally from such workflows, rather than from exceptional situations. If you imagine a different workflow and/or semantically different artifacts compared to the ones described, e.g., only a single underlying model which is continuously updated or a non-stage-based workflow, please also describe that in your challenge responses and how it influences the arising inconsistency management scenarios.

2.3. Inconsistency Management Scenarios

This challenge focuses on inconsistencies that are *known, documented, and intentionally tolerated* for a certain period of time.

Cross-Domain Analogy. Although the case study is framed in the context of automotive brake systems, the described inconsistency situations are not domain-specific. For example, in a medical infusion pump system, a safety requirement on maximum dosage may be updated based on clinical studies, while control logic and verification artifacts still reflect older assumptions. Similarly, in an industrial automation system, sensor accuracy assumptions may remain uncertain while safety margins are already specified. Participants from other domains are encouraged to reinterpret the artifacts and scenarios accordingly, while preserving the underlying inconsistency management challenges.

2.3.1. Parameter Mismatch as a Long-Running Inconsistency

A typical inconsistency arises when a braking pressure limit is updated in the control and calibration model based on new test results, while the functional model and the requirements model still reflect the old limit. Due to ongoing validation activities, this inconsistency is accepted and remains unresolved over multiple development iterations.

Participants should discuss:

- How they represent the inconsistency explicitly?
- How its scope and impact are assessed?
- How are stakeholders continuously informed about its existence?

2.3.2. Uncertainty-Induced Inconsistencies

Early in development, sensor accuracy assumptions in the structural model may contradict safety margins defined in the requirements model. The exact sensor characteristics have not yet been finalized, resulting in uncertainty rather than a clear error.

Participants should discuss:

- How they model inconsistencies under uncertainty?
- How they distinguish provisional from critical inconsistencies?
- How they support decision-making under incomplete information?

2.3.3. Evolving Strictness over Time

As the brake system progresses through development phases (e.g., concept, prototype, series production), the tolerance for inconsistencies decreases. An inconsistency that is acceptable at a low technological readiness level becomes unacceptable later.

Participants should discuss:

- How inconsistency severity evolves over time?
- How increasing strictness is enforced?
- How unresolved inconsistencies are escalated?

2.3.4. Variants and Fielded Systems

Variants of the brake system may be deployed in vehicles already in use, while new variants are under development. Aligning models of fielded systems with updated designs can introduce inconsistencies that cannot be resolved immediately.

Participants should discuss:

- How is the long-term coexistence of inconsistent variants handled?
- How is traceability between deployed and evolving models implemented?
- How is the inconsistency management made risk-aware?

3. Conclusion

Submissions to this challenge should discuss how their approach supports the explicit management of inconsistencies in the brake system case. In particular, authors are encouraged to address:

- which types of inconsistencies are supported and which are not,
- how long-running inconsistencies are tolerated and monitored,
- how explanations and decision support are provided,
- and what limitations remain.

Participants should also reflect on lessons learned and outline how their approach could evolve to better support inconsistency-aware engineering of complex, safety-critical systems.

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